

RISK FACTORS ASSOCIATED WITH SELF-PERCEPTION OF NEGATIVE SLEEP QUALITY IN HIGH SCHOOLS STUDENTS

FACTORES DE RIESGO ASOCIADOS A LA AUTOPERCEPCIÓN DE LA CALIDAD NEGATIVA DEL SUEÑO EN ESTUDIANTES DE SECUNDARIA

FATORES DE RISCOS ASSOCIADOS À AUTOPERCEPÇÃO DA QUALIDADE NEGATIVA DO SONO EM ESCOLARES DO ENSINO MÉDIO

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Abstract

This study aimed to investigate sociodemographic and lifestyle factors associated with negative self-perception of sleep quality among public high school students in Jequié, Bahia, Brazil. This is a descriptive-analytical study with a probabilistic sample of 1,170 adolescents. Data were collected using a validated questionnaire and analyzed using Poisson regression. The prevalence of negative sleep perception was 30.7%. After adjusted analysis, excessive computer screen time during the week (≥ 2 h/day) was significantly associated with negative sleep perception (PR=1.09; 95%CI: 1.01–1.18; $p=0.02$), whereas alcohol consumption showed an inverse association (PR=0.92; 95%CI: 0.86–0.98; $p=0.02$). It is concluded that excessive

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screen use is a modifiable risk factor. The inverse association with alcohol consumption requires cautious interpretation, considering potential biases and the known health risks of this behavior. The findings highlight the need for intersectoral strategies aimed at promoting sleep hygiene, responsible technology use, and health education in school settings, involving professionals, families, and the community as co-participants in adolescent health care.

Keywords: Behavior; Screen time; Sleep; Alcohol drinking; Adolescent.

Resumen

Este estudio tuvo como objetivo investigar los factores sociodemográficos y de estilo de vida asociados con la autopercepción negativa de la calidad del sueño en estudiantes de secundaria de escuelas públicas de Jequié, Bahía, Brasil. Se trata de un estudio descriptivo-analítico con una muestra probabilística de 1.170 adolescentes. Los datos fueron recolectados mediante un cuestionario validado y analizados mediante regresión de Poisson. La prevalencia de percepción negativa del sueño fue del 30,7%. Tras el análisis ajustado, el uso excesivo del ordenador durante la semana (≥ 2 h/día) mostró una asociación significativa con la percepción negativa del sueño (RP=1,09; IC95%: 1,01–1,18; p=0,02), mientras que el consumo de bebidas alcohólicas presentó una asociación inversa (RP=0,92; IC95%: 0,86–0,98; p=0,02). Se concluye que el uso prolongado de pantallas constituye un factor de riesgo modificable. La relación inversa con el consumo de alcohol requiere una interpretación cautelosa, debido a posibles sesgos y a los riesgos conocidos asociados a dicha sustancia. Los hallazgos señalan la necesidad de estrategias intersectoriales dirigidas a promover la higiene del sueño, el uso consciente de tecnologías y la educación para la salud en el entorno escolar, involucrando a profesionales, familias y comunidad como copartícipes en el cuidado de la salud de los adolescentes.

Palabras clave: Comportamiento; Tiempo de pantalla; Dormir; Consumo de alcohol; Adolescentes.

Resumo

Este estudo teve como objetivo investigar fatores sociodemográficos e de estilo de vida associados à autopercepção negativa da qualidade do sono em escolares do ensino médio da rede pública de Jequié, Bahia. Trata-se de estudo descritivo-analítico, com amostra probabilística de 1.170 adolescentes. Os dados foram coletados por meio de questionário validado e analisados por regressão de Poisson. A prevalência de percepção negativa do sono foi de 30,7%. Após análise ajustada, o tempo excessivo diante do computador durante a semana (≥ 2 h/dia) mostrou associação significativa com percepção negativa do sono (RP=1,09; IC95%: 1,01–1,18; p=0,02), enquanto o consumo de bebidas alcoólicas apresentou associação inversa (RP=0,92; IC95%: 0,86–0,98; p=0,02). Conclui-se que o uso prolongado de telas constitui fator de risco modificável. A relação inversa com o consumo de álcool exige cautela na interpretação, dada a possibilidade de vieses e os riscos conhecidos associados à substância. Os achados apontam para a necessidade de estratégias intersetoriais voltadas à promoção da higiene do sono, ao uso consciente de tecnologias e à educação em saúde no ambiente escolar, envolvendo profissionais, famílias e comunidade como coparticipantes no cuidado à saúde dos adolescentes.

Palavras-chave: Comportamento; Tempo de tela; Sono; Consumo de álcool; Adolescentes.

Introduction

Sleep disorders have been observed in epidemiological studies as important factors related to clinical outcomes, including metabolic dysfunctions and other health problems in schools (Cao *et al.*, 2022; Sharma *et al.*, 2021; Stiglic; Viner, 2019). The quality of nighttime sleep is considered a relevant ally in the process of physical growth, development, and maturation of adolescents, being seen as a source of revitalization for physiological and mental functions (Dutil *et al.*, 2022; Silva *et al.*, 2017).

Factors related to biological maturation in adolescents can lead to a decrease in sleep patterns due to the slower inhibition of melatonin secretion at the beginning of the light phase of the day, especially in the later stages of puberty (Andersen *et al.*, 2025). Furthermore, the slower accumulation of sleepiness throughout the day can result in excessive daytime sleepiness (Goldstein; Goldstein, 2024).

Adolescence is a life cycle marked by significant biopsychosocial impacts, including on the biological clock, commonly called the circadian rhythm, which can induce endogenous, social, and environmental changes (Pifer; Ferrara; Kwapis, 2024). Delayed sleep onset during puberty may be related to changes in lifestyle, social relationships, and morning school routines (Diogo *et al.*, 2024). These factors contribute to alterations in the natural sleep rhythm (Trindade; Ramos, 2020). It is precisely during this phase that adolescents begin to develop behavioral patterns that are often considered appropriate (Saúde Mental [...], 2025).

Among students, high school students tend to be more occupied with daily tasks and social activities. This stage of education demands more complex academic work, and adolescents with chronic sleep deprivation or inadequate sleep tend to exhibit poorer daytime and academic performance (Bajerski *et al.*, 2022). As students progress through the grades, patterns of reduced sleep are observed. Some scientific evidence indicates that sleep needs change during the life cycle (Bajerski *et al.*, 2022;

Brown *et al.*, 2022; Howie *et al.*, 2020). When nighttime sleep duration is less than seven hours, alertness and academic performance are objectively impaired, affecting normal development and quality of life (Keenan; Van Gundy, 2021).

Sleep is considered a key component of learning and memory, directly influencing hormonal regulation and behavior. Several studies have identified a significant relationship between sleep deprivation and habits detrimental to well-being, such as the consumption of illicit substances and alcoholic beverages, sedentary behaviors, inadequate diet, and physical inactivity. Among adolescent behaviors, regular physical activity, healthy eating habits (such as the consumption of fruits and vegetables), and less screen time (television, smartphones, computers, etc) seems to contribute to a better perception of sleep quality. On the other hand, unhealthy behaviors, such as alcohol and tobacco consumption and sedentary lifestyles, are associated with greater exposure to negative self-perception of sleep quality (Gajardo *et al.*, 2021; Maciel *et al.*, 2023).

In the Brazilian context, there is a lack of national Research focused on this Population subgroup, although studies conducted in the South and Northeast regions indicate that 45.7% of adolescents reported a negative perception of sleep (Silva *et al.*, 2017). Poor sleep quality may be associated with the presence of mental disorders such as depression, stress, and anxiety (Anoosha *et al.*, 2025).

Until today, studies on the association between negative self-perception of sleep quality and related factors in adolescents in Brazil are limited in number and focus on specific populations. These investigations do not consider the particular needs of each region, nor the cultural and sociodemographic contrasts, which are directly related to simultaneous exposure to health risk factors.

Given the aspects above, the main objective of this study was to investigate behavioral factors, lifestyle, and their possible association with the perception of sleep quality in high school students from the public school system in the city of Jequié, Bahia, Brazil.

Methods

This is a descriptive-analytical, school-based study derived from monitoring health risk behaviors in schoolchildren in the city of Jequié, Bahia, Brazil. The sample composition used cluster Random sampling for a finite population (Barbosa Filho; Campos; Lopes, 2012).

Initially, 3.040 students were selected, distributed across 98 classes from all state public schools in the municipality, all duly enrolled in regular high school. Subsequently, stratified classes were selected with probability proportional to the size of the schools. That is, Through a draw, 48 classes were chosen from the 98 existing ones, totaling 1.363 students, considering an average of 31 students per class. According to the exclusion criteria, 193 students were removed from the analysis. Exclusions refer to dropouts, incomplete data, and the absence of authorization from parents or guardians. The final sample of the study included 1.170 students. Data collection took place in July and August 2015.

In this study, all schools offering regular secondary education in the morning and afternoon shifts in the urban area of the municipality were included ($n=12$), with no refusal to participate from school administrators. Schools in rural areas, those offering Only Evening classes, and the Military College were excluded, as its Physical Education teaching model differs from that adopted in other regular schools.

The parameter for determining the sample size was the estimated prevalence of the phenomenon, set at 50% due to the high number of variables to be analyzed. The Confidence interval adopted was 95%, with a maximum error of three percentage points. For this sampling design, the Random cluster sampling calculation for a finite Population was used, including the design effect, whose value was multiplied by 1.5. Additionally, 15% was considered for losses or refusals (Raggio; Magnanini, 2000).

An adapted questionnaire, referring to self-reported health risk behaviors in schools, based on a previously validated instrument (COMPAC), was used, Applied by

experienced researchers. The application lasted, on average, 28 minutes per classroom (Silva *et al.*, 2013).

The Variable “self-perception of sleep quality” was measured with the following question: “How often do you consider that you sleep well?”. For analysis purposes, the perception of sleep quality was dichotomized into positive (always and almost always) and negative (sometimes, almost never and never) (Silva *et al.*, 2013).

The sociodemographic variables included were: sex (male and female); age range in complete Years, later dichotomized into “<16 years” and “≥16 years”; occupation (works and does not work); marital status (single or married); mother’s education (< 8 years of schooling and ≥ years of schooling) and monthly family income (< 2 minimum wages and ≥ 2 minimum wages). At the time of data collection, the minimum wage was R\$788.00.

To evaluate sedentary behavior, questions about screen time were used: “How many hours a day do you watch TV during the week and/or on weekends?” and “How many hours a day do you use the computer during the week and/or on weekends?”, with response options “less than or equal to 2 hours” and “more than two hours”.

To identify the level of physical activity, a question about Frequency and another about duration of practice were used. Those who did not accumulate the minimum recommended five days per week, with at least 60 minutes per day of moderate to vigorous intensity physical activity, were classified as insufficiently active (Silva *et al.*, 2013; Spring; Moller; Coons, 2012).

Regarding fruit and vegetable consumption, the criterion used was the intake of at least one serving per day, categorized as inadequate consumption (“< 5 days/week”) and adequate consumption (“≥ 5 days/week”) (Silva *et al.*, 2013). Alcohol consumption was considered regardless of the number of drinks, being categorized as “yes” and “no”. For tobacco consumption, the criterion adopted was also independent of the quantity of cigarettes consumed, similarly categorized as “yes” and “no” (Bernardo *et al.*, 2009).

Statistical analysis employed *Poisson regression* with robust variance, complementing the modeling of prevalent phases in cross-sectional studies. The dependent variable consisted of negative self-perception of sleep quality,

categorized as “yes” and “no”. Independent variables included sociodemographic characteristics such as sex, age, occupation, marital status, maternal education, and family income, as well as lifestyle-related behaviors, including physical activity level screen time, and consumption of fruits, vegetables, alcohol, and tobacco. A crude analysis was performed to estimate the Prevalence Ratio (PR) and the respective 95% Confidence Intervals (95% CI). The analysis included in the multivariate model only variables with a p-value < 0.20 in the crude analysis, to control for potential confounding variables, as recommended by Barbosa Filho; Campos; Lopes (2012). The significance level was $p < 0.05$.

This study was conducted in accordance with Resolution n° 466/2012 of the National Health Council, which regulates research involving human being in Brazil. The original research protocol was approved by the Research Ethics Committee with Human Being of the State University of Southwest Bahia (UESB) in 2014, under an opinion number that, due to limitations of the Plataforma Brasil system, is currently not available for public consultation. In 2022, the project was re-evaluated and approved for the continuation and updating of data collection, under a new opinion number: 5662326 and CAAE: 33526014.1.0000.0055. All students submitted duly designed Consent and Assent Forms. In the case of minors under 18 years of age, parents or guardian signed the respective forms.

Results

The largest proportions identified among the students were: age under 16 years (52.1%), female (57.9%), and single marital status (88.5%). In addition, 71.3% reported having a family income of less than two minimum wages.

Regarding lifestyle, regardless of gender, it was observed that 81.5% of participants were physically inactive; 60.8% reported inadequate consumption of vegetables, and 54.8% of fruits. Furthermore, 23.8% reported consuming at least one glass of alcoholic beverage, and 5.9% reported having the habit of smoking,

regardless of the number of cigarettes consumed per day. The descriptive characteristics of the participants are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 – Descriptive characteristics of the sample. Jequié, Bahia, Brazil, 2015.

Variables	N°	%
Dependents		
Sleep		
Positive perception of sleep	809	69,3
Negative perceptio of sleep	359	30,7
Independents		
Sociodemographic		
Sex		
Masculine	491	42,1
Feminine	678	57,9
Age (years)		
< 16	609	52,1
≥ 16	561	47,9
Occupation		
Does not work	952	81,4
He/She Works	218	18,6
Marital status		
Single	1035	88,5
Married	135	11,5
Mother´s education level (years of schooling)		
< 8 years	445	38,0
> 8 years	725	62,0
Monthly Family income		
< 02 Minimum wages	834	71,3
> 02 Minimum wages	336	28,7
Lifestyle		
Level of physical activity		
Insufficient	953	81,5
Enough	217	18,5
Screen time (TV/week)		
≥ 02 hours/day	381	32,8
< 02 hours/day	782	67,2
Screen time (TV/weekend)		
≥ 02 hours/day	461	40,2
< 02 hours/day	685	59,8
Screen time (Computer/week)		
≥ 02 hours/day	317	27,3
< 02 hourss/day	846	72,7
Screen time (Computer/weekend)		
≥ 02 hours/day	426	37,2
< 02 hours/day	720	62,8
Fruit consumption		
Inadequate	634	54,8
Adequate	522	45,2
Vegetables consumption		
Inadequate	693	60,8
Adequate	446	39,2

Alcohol consumption		
Yes	277	23,8
No	887	76,2
Tobacco consumption		
Yes	69	5,9
No	1101	94,1

Source: Research data, 2015.

After crude analysis (Table 2), negative sleep perception showed a significant association with work occupation (PR = 0.94; 95% CI: 0.89-1.02), mother's education (PR = 0.95; 95% CI: 0.90-1.00), family income (PR = 0.94; 95% CI: 0.89-1.02), computer screen time during the week (PR = 0.89; 95% CI: 0.84-0.94), computer screen time during the weekend (PR = 0.91; 95% CI: 0.86-0.96), fruit consumption (PR=1.04; 95% CI: 0.98-1.06) and alcohol consumption (PR = 1.10; 95% CI: 1.03 – 1.17).

Table 2 – Longitudinal association between sociodemographic and lifestyle variables in the perception of sleep quality during the week.

Variables	Sleep quality			
	Gross RP		Adjusted RP	
	IC95%	p	IC95%	p
Sex				
Masculine	1,02 (0,96-1,07)	0,55		
Feminine	1			
Age (years)				
< 16	0,98 (0,93-1,03)	0,45		
≥ 16	1			
Marital status				
Single	0,93(0,67-1,31)	0,69		
Married	1			
Occupation				
Does not work	0,94(0,89 -1,02)	0,11	0,95(0,88-1,01)	0,12
He/she works	1		1	
Mother's education level				
< 08 years of study	0,95(0,90-1,00)	0,07	0,96(0,91-1,02)	0,18
≥ 08 years of study	1		1	
Monthly Family income				
< 02 Salaries	0,94(0,89-1,02)	0,06	1,03 (0,97-1,10)	0,27
≥ 02 Salaries	1		1	
Weekly screen time (TV)				
≥ 02 hours/day	1,02(0,96-1,08)	0,52		
< 02 hours/day	1			
Weekend screen time (TV)				
≥ 02 hours/day	1,02(0,93-1,04)	0,54		
< 02 hours/day	1			
Weekly screen time (Computer)				
≥ 02 hours/day	0,89 (0,84-0,94)	0,00	1,09 (1,01-1,18)	0,02
< 02 hours/day	1		1	

Weekend screen time (Computer)				
≥ 02 hours/day	0,91(0,86-0,96)	0,01	0,97 (0,90-1,03)	0,31
< 02 hours/day	1		1	
Fruit consumption				
< 05 days/week	1,04(0,98-1,06)	0,19	0,97 (0,92-1,02)	0,26
≥ 05 days/week	1		1	
Vegetable consumption				
< 05 days/week	1,04(0,98-1,09)	0,21		
≥ 05 days/week	1			
Alcohol consumption				
Yes	1,10(1,03-1,17)	0,05	0,92(0,86-0,98)	0,02
No	1		1	
Tobacco consumption				
Yes	1,04(0,92-1,17)	0,52		
No	1			
Level of physical activity				
Insufficient	0,99(0,92-1,06)	0,78		
Sufficient (300 min/week)	1			

Source: Research data, 2015. **Note:** RP – prevalence ration; IC – Confidence interval; Values in bold: $p < 0,05$.

In the adjusted analysis behavior (SB) related to computer screen time (≥ 2 hours/day during the week) (PR = 1.09; 95% CI: 1.01 – 1.18) and alcohol consumption (PR = 0.92; 95% CI: 0.86 – 0.98) remained statistically significant ($p < 0.02$).

It was observed that frequent computer exposure for ≥ 2 hours/day increased the chance of negative sleep perception, while alcohol consumption showed an inverse association with the outcome (Table 2).

Discussion

Although the data used in this study predates the COVID-19 pandemic, it is important to highlight that, starting in 2020, there has been a worsening of sleep patterns and digital behavior among adolescents (Bothe *et al.*, 2022). Excessive screen use, especially at night, has been associated with increased insomnia, with negative impacts on academic performance and emotional health in adolescents (Sysło *et al.*, 2024; Adam; Replogle, 2021). Excessive screen use, especially at night, has been associated with increased insomnia, with negative impacts on academic performance and emotional health in adolescents (Han; Zhou; Liu, 2024). Although such changes cannot be directly analyzed in this study due to the temporal limitations

of the database, they highlight the relevance of the topic and reinforce the need for continuous monitoring of factors influencing sleep quality in this population.

Due to changes in their bodies and external influencers, such as school schedules, adolescents tend to sleep later, wake up later, and have more varied sleep patterns between school days and weekends (Vidal; Shochat, 2023). The prevalence of negative self-perception of sleep was found 30.7%. Estimates of this prevalence in adolescents vary significantly between national (Lima *et al.*, 2023; Souza Neto *et al.*, 2021) and international studies (Malloggi *et al.*, 2020; Ren *et al.*, 2021).

A systematic review, with studies conducted according to the PRISMA guidelines between January 1990 and December 2020, gathered 20 articles and identified that adolescents with lower socioeconomic status tend to present more sleep disorders. However, the evidence from the present study did not find a correlation between the sociodemographic indicators of adolescents and their self-perception of sleep quality (Bendaoud; Etindele Sosso, 2022).

The study found an inverse association between alcohol consumption and negative self-perception of sleep among schoolchildren. One hypothesis for this relationship is the consumption of alcoholic beverages on weekends, coupled with the possibility of waking up later without the need to adhere to rigid school schedules. However, it is recognized that excessive alcohol consumption during adolescence can lead to serious health risks, such as accidents, risky sexual behaviors, and exposure to infections (OECD, 2022). Furthermore, adolescents who consume alcohol frequently exhibit behavior such as competitiveness, exhibitionism, risk-seeking, and intense emotions, which is common at young ages (Pizzini, 2020). The relationship between sleep disorders and the use of alcohol as a relaxant may increase the risk of dependence and cognitive and behavioral impairments (Fipps; Sinha, 2023; Tussey; Wong, 2024).

Significant changes in sleep and wake times between weekdays and weekends may be associated with a negative perception of sleep. Evidence suggests that adolescents who consume alcohol should maintain regular sleep schedules to ensure better rest quality (Kwon; Seo; Hasler, 2023). However, alcohol consumption

during this phase of life may be associated with other negative consequences, such as difficulties in relationships with teachers, consumption of fatty foods, and poor academic performance (Silva *et al.*, 2021).

Changes in environmental, social, and behavioral factors directly impact sleep patterns, especially due to increased school demands. Regarding alcohol consumption, an international study identified a prevalence of 25.2% among adolescents (Farnia *et al.*, 2024), a value considerably lower than that observed in the national survey with schoolchildren which was 63.3% (Bezerra *et al.*, 2021).

Although our findings suggest that alcohol consumption is associated with a lower negative perception of sleep, a survey on parasomnia in adolescents shows a higher prevalence of excessive daytime sleepiness (EDS) among young people who consume alcoholic beverages, which can compromise school performance and the health of students (Barbosa *et al.*, 2020). There is agreement between our findings and studies conducted with schoolchildren in Pernambuco, which showed that the most prevalent lifestyle domains were inadequate eating habits, sedentary behavior, alcohol consumption, and smoking (Silva *et al.*, 2017).

Regarding Tobacco, even with low prevalence and lack of association with negative self-perception of sleep, early onset of consumption is a relevant indicator, since a large proportion of adult smokers started before the age of 18, which is associated with respiratory diseases and cancer (Choi *et al.*, 2023).

Sleep patterns can also be influenced by inadequate dietary habits, such as consuming soft drinks and stimulants before bed, which can lead to micronutrient deficiencies (Kelmanson, 2023). Although this study did not identify an association between negative self-perception of sleep quality and eating habits, the importance of future studies that further explore this relationship is recognized. Furthermore, alcohol consumption, smoking, and inadequate eating habits may be associated with another health risk behavior: excessive screen use (Nakshine *et al.*, 2022).

Studies have suggested an association between the time and type of screen exposure and sleep disorders (Chahine; Pelletier; Chahine, 2023; Santiago *et al.*, 2022). In our sample, screen time in front of the computer during the week proved to be a

risk factor for negative self-perception of sleep, with a prevalence of 27.3%. The highest frequencies of screen exposure were observed during weekends, however, without a statistically significant association with the outcome studies. A possible explanation for this finding would be the variation in Weekly routine, since, during school days, the intervals between sleeping and waking are more restricted, while on weekends this time tends to be longer.

Among Lebanese students, excessive screen use is linked to daytime fatigue, sleep delays, poor sleep quality; and lower academic performance, especially when devices are used before bed. The study showed that 90% of students had at least one electronic device in their bedroom and used it for more than four hours a day, resulting in fewer hours of nighttime sleep and greater daytime fatigue (Chahine; Pelletier; Chahine, 2023). Research conducted in Argentina with adolescents from 52 schools demonstrated that screen use, such as video games and cell phones, can reduce nighttime sleep and increase daytime sleep. Those who spent more time playing games slept less and showed greater daytime fatigue. The use of mobile devices was associated with poor academic performance, especially in language and mathematics (Pérez-Chada *et al.*, 2023).

Anxious adolescents showed poorer sleep quality associated with screen time, especially with interactive devices. It was identified that 10.4% of adolescents with intensive computer or video game use reported sleep problems, and 76.5% likely presented symptoms of anxiety (Santiago *et al.*, 2022). A study conducted during the COVID-19 pandemic identified a statistically significant association between high screen time (≥ 5 hours/day) and the occurrence of sleep disorders in adolescents, indicating that those with greater screen time were approximately 3.8 times more likely to develop sleep disorders compared to those with less screen time (Windiani *et al.*, 2021). One suggested mechanism is the influence of artificial light from screens on melatonin production, which alters the circadian rhythm and compromises physiological functions. Excessive screen exposure tends to reduce rest duration and increase lethargy, contributing to a negative perception of sleep (Viola *et al.*, 2023).

Among the Limitations of this study, the use of a questionnaire, even though validated and tested, stands out, as it may overestimate or underestimate the prevalence of behavior. Strengths include the representative sample and the fact that this is the first epidemiological survey on negative self-perception of sleep quality, with separate analysis by type of screen exposure in the investigated municipality.

Adolescents excessively exposed to computer screens during the week were more likely to report a negative perception of their sleep. Additionally, alcohol consumption was observed as a protective factor against the self-reported outcome. The results demonstrate that the observed behaviors are modifiable. This reinforces the need to implement strategies aimed at promoting sleep hygiene, reducing screen time, and addressing other risk factors. Families and schools play a fundamental role in developing educational plans that emphasize the importance of healthy sleep among adolescents.

Adolescentes expostos excessivamente à tela do computador durante a semana apresentaram maior probabilidade de relatar percepção negativa do sono. Adicionalmente, a ingestão de bebidas alcoólicas foi observada como fator de proteção para o desfecho autorreferido. Os resultados demonstram que os comportamentos observados são modificáveis. Isso reforça a necessidade de implementação de estratégias voltadas à promoção da higiene do sono, redução do tempo de tela e enfrentamento de outros fatores de risco. Famílias e escolas desempenham papel fundamental no desenvolvimento de planos educacionais que valorizem a importância do sono saudável entre adolescentes.

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